

**LENTICULAR ALGEBRO-GEOMETRIC
CONTINUOUS POINT-MOTION (OR GEODETIC LINE):
ON THE RICCI & KÄHLER–RICCI FLOW OVER TIME**

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ABSTRACT. The purpose of this article is to investigate the Ricci flow and its Kählerian version. We would like to underline the aspect that we could call *lenticular* of this geometric object (consisting of a specific partial differential equation), the possibility of modifying the shapes of space through it; also, an hint to the optimality of such a flow, viz. the specificity of being described in terms of optimal transport. The Kähler–Ricci flow as a parabolic complex Monge–Ampère formula is then defined, followed by a theorem on the geometric curvature evolution. In closing, there is a supporting appendix.^a

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^a Athena leaped from Jupiter’s head (*Tum quoque, cūm Pallas cerebro Jovis excidit, aurum*), right? This article jumps out from the Chap. 10 of [28], but develops unpublished *ponderationes*, and goes its own way.

1. Repetitions on the Hamilton's Ricci Flow

Let us start with some preliminary notions.

(1) The Ricci flow was introduced by R.S. Hamilton [16], and we can write as

$$\phi_{\mathbb{R}}^{\text{unn}} \begin{cases} \frac{\partial g_t}{\partial t} = -2\text{Ric}(g_t), & g_t \stackrel{\text{viz}}{=} g(t), \\ \partial_t g_{\mu\nu}(t) = -2R_{\mu\nu}(t), \\ \text{with the initial condition } g(0) = g_0, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$\phi_{\mathbb{R}}^{\text{nor}} \begin{cases} \frac{\partial g_t}{\partial t} = -2\text{Ric}(g_t) + \frac{2}{n}R_{(a)}g_t, & g_t \stackrel{\text{viz}}{=} g(t), \\ \partial_t g_{\mu\nu} = -2R_{\mu\nu} + \frac{2}{n}R_{(a)}g_{\mu\nu}, \\ \text{with the initial condition } g(0) = g_0, \text{ and } R_{(a)} = \frac{\int_{\mathcal{M}^n} R_s d\mu}{\int_{\mathcal{M}^n} d\mu}, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $g_t \stackrel{\text{viz}}{=} g(t)$ and $g_{\mu\nu}$ denote the Riemannian metric, *smoothly* structured in some interval

$$t \in [0, T) \subset \mathbb{R},$$

with $T \in (0, \infty]$, Ric (notation without indices) and $R_{\mu\nu}$ (notation with indices) are the two notations for the the Ricci curvature tensor (Margo 1.1), which gives its name [18] to the flow, whereas \mathcal{M} is a smooth n -manifold. Plainly, g_t is a solution to $\phi_{\mathbb{R}}$ (Ricci flow)—on the basis of Eqq. (1) or (2)—for an arbitrary \mathcal{C}^∞ initial metric g_0 .

(2) Eqq. (1) and (2) are the unnormalized and normalized versions of $\phi_{\mathbb{R}}$, respectively. The normalized flow is a *volume preserving* equation with respect to g_t , in which, for a smooth measure μ , the differential element $d\mu$ is the *volume element*, or density δ , i.e.

$$d\mu = \begin{cases} \delta(x)dx = \delta(x)dx^1, \dots, dx^n, & \text{in local coordinates,} \\ \sqrt{\det(g_{\mu\nu})}dx, \end{cases} \quad (3a)$$

$$(3b)$$

where dx is the volume element in \mathbb{R}^n , and $R_{(a)}$ is the average of the scalar curvature, with the Ricci scalar [33] [34]

$$R_s \in \mathcal{C}^\infty(\mathcal{M}) \stackrel{\text{id}}{=} \begin{cases} \text{tr}(\text{Ric}), \\ R^\mu{}_\mu = g^{\mu\nu}R_{\mu\nu} = R_\nu{}^\nu, \\ g^{\mu\xi}g^{\nu\varrho}R_{\mu\nu\xi\varrho}. \end{cases} \quad (4a)$$

$$(4b)$$

$$(4c)$$

(In words, R_s is the trace of the Ricci curvature tensor, with respect to the Riemannian metric g . The scalar curvature represents the most elementary of *local invariants* of g on \mathcal{M}).

(3) Eq. (1), more appropriately, is a *quasi-linear weakly parabolic equation*.

Margo 1.1 (Ricci curvature tensor). The Ricci (curvature) tensor [32] is a tool that is used to measure the *degree of flatness* or the *value of non-flatness* of a certain surface, so the difference between non-Euclidean space, or curved space, under the Riemannian geometry, and Euclidean space, whose curvature is zero. E. Bompiani [2] was the first to introduce officially the expression *Ricci (curvature) tensor*.

The Ricci tensor is a symmetric tensor of rank 2, and it can be written in at least four ways. Let us get specific.

(1) Its three primary forms:

$$\text{Ric} \stackrel{\text{id}}{=} \begin{cases} R_\nu{}^\mu \vec{E}_\mu \otimes \vartheta^\nu \text{ as a } \binom{1}{1}\text{-tensor,} \\ R_{\nu\xi} \vartheta^\nu \otimes \vartheta^\xi = g_{\nu\mu} R_\xi{}^\mu \vartheta^\nu \otimes \vartheta^\xi \text{ as a } \binom{0}{2}\text{-tensor,} \\ R^{\mu\xi} \vec{E}_\mu \otimes \vec{E}_\xi = g^{\mu\nu} \vec{E}_\mu \otimes \vec{E}_\xi \text{ as a } \binom{2}{0}\text{-tensor,} \end{cases} \quad (5a)$$

$$(5b)$$

$$(5c)$$

i.e.

$$\text{Ric} \in \begin{cases} \mathbb{T}_1^1(\mathcal{M}), & (6a) \\ \mathbb{T}_2^0(\mathcal{M}), & (6b) \\ \mathbb{T}_0^2(\mathcal{M}). & (6c) \end{cases}$$

(2) The Ricci tensor correlates to a *contraction* of the Riemann curvature tensor:

$$\text{Ric} \stackrel{\text{i6}}{=} \begin{cases} R_{\nu}{}^{\mu} \vec{E}_{\mu} \otimes \vartheta^{\nu} = R_{\mu\xi}{}^{\xi\nu} \vec{E}_{\mu} \otimes \vartheta^{\nu} = R_{\mu\xi\zeta}{}^{\nu} g^{\zeta\xi} \vec{E}_{\mu} \otimes \vartheta^{\nu}, & (7a) \\ R_{\mu\nu} \vartheta^{\mu} \otimes \vartheta^{\nu} = g^{\xi\rho} R_{\mu\xi\rho\nu} \vartheta^{\mu} \otimes \vartheta^{\nu}. & (7b) \end{cases}$$

(3) In an explicit solution, making use of the Christoffel symbols:

$$\text{Ric} \stackrel{\text{i6}}{=} R_{\mu\nu} = \partial_{\xi} \Gamma_{\mu\nu}{}^{\xi} - \partial_{\nu} \Gamma_{\mu\xi}{}^{\xi} + \Gamma_{\mu\nu}{}^{\xi} \Gamma_{\xi\rho}{}^{\rho} - \Gamma_{\mu\xi}{}^{\rho} \Gamma_{\nu\rho}{}^{\xi}. \quad (8)$$

(4) Ricci curvature, as a $\binom{0}{2}$ -tensor, is also termed as the trace of a linear operator $\vec{Z} \mapsto R_{\vec{X},\vec{Z}}\vec{Y}$, so

$$\text{Ric}(\vec{X}, \vec{Y}) = \text{tr} \left(\vec{Z} \mapsto R_{\vec{X},\vec{Z}}\vec{Y} \right). \quad (9)$$

It is with this in view that we say that Ric is a trace of the Riemann curvature tensor. *

1.1. The Lenticular Aspect of the Ricci Flow

The Ricci flow is a *geometric flow* with *algebro-geometric* characterizations, or even a *gradient flow* for a given functional, such as the one of Einstein–Hilbert (32), on an n -space of Riemannian metric.

More explicitly, it is a *evolutionary process* that *stretches*, or *expands*, the metric g of a manifold in directions corresponding to *negative coefficients of the Ricci tensor*, and *contracts*, or *shrinks*, g in directions corresponding to *positive coefficients of the Ricci tensor*.^a

This is why Hamilton, by analogy, associates (1) with a *heat-like equation* in a tensor guise, although the geometric flow is *quasi-linear*, here; and then he compares $\phi_{\mathbb{R}}$ to a *Laplacian operator* Δ of the Riemannian metric.^b

It is from this stretching & shrinking processes, for a evolution of curvature, that the *lenticular aspect* of the flow emerges, that is, like a *crystal* that enlarges and/or reduces—zoom in & out—an image.

Which is perfectly consistent, when one advances through the alternation of physico-theoretical abstractions and algebro-spatial structures of Hamilton’s Riccian flow, in the discovery of what underlies the fundamental forces of nature (whether order or chaos dominates), with G. Perelman’s [29, p. 3] ruminations:

The Ricci flow has also been discussed in quantum field theory, as an approximation to the renormalization group (RG) flow for the two-dimensional nonlinear σ -model^c [...]. I would like to speculate on the Wilsonian picture [37] [38] of the RG flow. In this picture, t corresponds to the scale parameter; the larger is t , the larger is the distance scale and the smaller is the energy scale [...].^d In other words, decreasing of t should correspond to looking at our Space through a microscope with higher resolution, where Space is now described not by some ([R]iemannian or any other) metric, but by an hierarchy of [R]iemannian metrics, connected by the Ricci flow equation. Note that we have a paradox here: the regions that appear to be far from each other at larger distance scale may become close at smaller distance scale; moreover, if we allow Ricci flow through singularities, the regions that are in different connected components at larger distance scale may become neighboring when viewed through microscope. Anyway, this connection between the Ricci flow and the RG flow suggests that Ricci flow must be gradient-like.

^a The metric is *stationary* under $\phi_{\mathbb{R}}$ if there is a Ricci-flat metric (Ric = 0).

^b Cf. Hamilton [19, p. 7]: «[S]ome geometrical object can be improved by evolving it with a parabolic partial differential equation. In the Ricci Flow we try to improve a Riemannian metric $g(x, y)$ by evolving it by its Ricci curvature $Rc(x, y)$ under the equation $\frac{\partial}{\partial t} g(X, Y) = -2Rc(X, Y)$. In local geodesic coordinates $\{x^i\}$ at a point $P[.]$ where the metric is $ds^2 = g_{ij} dx^i dx^j[.]$ we find that the ordinary Laplacian of the metric is “ Δ ” $g_{ij} = g^{pq} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^p \partial x^q} g_{ij} = -2Rc(X, Y)[.]$ so the Ricci flow is [or rather, resembles] really the heat equation for a Riemannian metric $\frac{\partial}{\partial t} g = “\Delta” g$ ».

^c So named by M. Gell-Mann and M. Lévy [15, p. 717] because of the scalar meson σ , as already established by J. Schwinger [35].

^d «[T]o compute something on a lower energy scale one has to average the contributions of the degrees of freedom, corresponding to the higher energy scale» (ibid.). Perelman [29, p. 12] then goes on to identify a *statistical analogy*, which is «related to the description of the renormalization group flow»; in one case «one obtains various quantities by averaging over higher energy states», whereas in the other «those states are suppressed by the exponential factor [...]. The interplay of statistical physics and (pseudo)-[R]iemannian geometry occurs in the subject of Black Hole Thermodynamics, developed by Hawking et al.».

And it is no coincidence that a first definition, although still not explicit and collateral, of the Ricci flow, under the approach later known as *Ricci-DeTurck* [8] in the Hamilton's system, as well as a proto-description of the Ricci soliton, are not in differential geometry, but both are descended from quantum field theory, for work of D.H. Friedan [13] [14].^a

Friedan's attention, being a physicist (and not a mathematician), is mainly paid to a generalization of the non-linear σ -model (part of particle physics, see footnote c on p. 3, aimed at theorising *quantum strings* flowing in a dynamic arena of space-time),^b pushing forward on the ideas of J. Honerkamp [22] and A.M. Polyakov [30].

1.2. Analogy with Thermal Diffusion: Heat-like Penetration for Harmonic Maps

Hamilton's idea [16, p. 256] is blatantly inspired by the Eels–Sampson [9] *harmonic mapping* of Riemannian spaces,

$$\varphi_v: \mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathcal{N},$$

leading to deformations of maps by the classical *heat* (or *diffusion*) *equation*,

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} = \alpha_{\mathbb{T}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x_1^2} + \cdots + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x_n^2} \right), \quad (10)$$

$$v_t = \alpha_{\mathbb{T}} \Delta v, \quad v_t = \Delta v, \quad (11a)$$

$$v_t - \Delta v = 0, \quad (11b)$$

$$\Delta = \nabla^2 v - \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} = 0, \quad (11c)$$

which can then either be written with spatial and temporal variables (10), or in Laplacian form (11), where

$$v: \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad v = v(x_1, \dots, x_n, t) = v(x, t), \quad (12)$$

is a function reliably identifiable with the temperature \mathbb{T} , defined on an open (sub)set $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, $x \in \Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, $t \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $\alpha_{\mathbb{T}}$ is the thermal diffusivity, namely the rate of diffusion for the medium through which heat flows (when we say that the heat *flows* in a medium, we clearly use a liquid analogy), and $\Delta = \nabla^2 = \nabla \cdot \nabla$ is the Laplacian. The Eels–Sampson *harmonic map heat flow*, for the associated energy functional, is the same as a *gradient flow*.

Margo 1.2 (Calor et geometria). Riemann [31] is an explicit forerunner of such an association, establishing a relationship between *physical results (heat conduction problem)* and *differential geometry issues*.^c *

1.3. What is it for? The Magic of the Variation of the Shapes of Space

Ricci flow is chiefly used to *deform a (Riemannian) space* for *non-linear/quasi-linear evolutions*, in order to better handle this space, in purely geometric terms, or analytically.

Being some sort of *quantity of evolution*, it is a mathematical tool for *creating, controlling, or transforming*, within certain limits, the *shapes of space*, and its *volume growth*, also following geodesic paths; and, finally, the Ricci flow is a tool for *flattening-smoothing*, at least locally, possible *irregularities* inherent in the topological space under examination.

Hamilton investigates the Ricci flow properties on 2- [18], 3- [16] and 4-manifolds [17], focusing on metrics of *strictly positive/non-negative* Ricci curvature.

^a Cf. Friedan [14, pp. 390-391, 318]: «The infinitesimal form of the renormalization group [flow] is the renormalization group equation $\frac{d}{dt} g_{ij} = -\beta_{ij}(g)$, where β is a vector field on [the space] $\tilde{\mathbf{R}}$ [of Riemannian metrics], called the β -function. The tangent vector $\beta(g)$ to the space of metrics at g is the symmetric tensor field $\beta_{ij}(g)$ on [the manifold] M [...]. When M is a homogeneous space G/H [the quotient G/H of a Lie group G by a compact subgroup H], the β -function is shown to be a gradient on the finite[-]dimensional space of G -invariant metric couplings on M . And, when M is a two[-]dimensional compact manifold, the β -function is shown to be a gradient on the infinite[-]dimensional space of metrics on M ».

^b For an in-depth study and advances on the connection between the non-linear σ -model and the Ricci flow, see the writings of M. Carfora [3] [4] [5] [6, chap. 4].

^c See Riemann [31, pp. 370, 382]: «[P]roperties of a body determining the conduction of heat and distribution of heat, such that there is a system of lines which remain isothermal [...]. These investigations may be illustrated with some geometrical interpretation, though this is founded on unusual concepts ([Q]uales esse debeant proprietates corporis motum caloris determinantes et distributio caloris, ut detur systema linearum quae semper isothermae maneant [...]. Disquisitiones haec interpretatione quadam geometrica illustrari possunt, quae quamquam conceptibus inusitatis nitatur)».

1.4. Optimality of the Ricci Flow

The Ricci flow is characterized by an *optimal transportation*, as demonstrated, step by step, by J. Lott [25], McCann–Topping [26] & P. Topping [36].

In these papers it is shown that there is a *convexity property* for the entropy function along Wasserstein geodesic (and Wasserstein-types distance), called *ℓ -optimal transportation*—in this way a new demonstration of monotonicity of Perelman’s reduced volume is given. This implies the existence of a monotonicity relationship between Ricci flow and optimal transportation, with reference to Perelman’s entropy \mathcal{F} -functional (or entropy-energy \mathcal{F} -functional) and Perelman’s entropy \mathcal{W} -functional (or entropy-energy \mathcal{W} -functional), which are monotone and monotonically increasing (or non-decreasing) quantities, respectively, see [28, sec. 10.4.1].

The whole is unequivocally connected to the fundamental notion of ℓ -length, introduced by Perelman [29, sec. 7]; the latter is an energy-like functional, namely a local length functional defined on the space of all space-time curves, and is related to a better understanding of Riccian flow singularities. The ℓ -length can be defined by such an equation:

$$\ell(\gamma_c) = \int_{\tau_1}^{\tau_2} \sqrt{\tau} \left\{ R_{s_{g_\tau}}(\gamma_c(\tau)) + \left| \frac{d\gamma_c}{d\tau} \right|_{g_\tau}^2 \right\} d\tau, \quad (13a)$$

$$= \int_{\tau_1}^{\tau_2} \sqrt{\tau} \{ R_{s_{g_\tau}}(\gamma_c(\tau)) + |\dot{\gamma}_c(\tau)|_{g_\tau}^2 \} d\tau, \quad \dot{\gamma}_c(\tau) = \partial_\tau \gamma_c(\tau) \stackrel{\text{viz}}{=} \frac{\partial \gamma_c}{\partial \tau}, \quad (13b)$$

where the metric g_τ is used at time $t_0 - \tau$ for both the Ricci scalar $R_{s_{g_\tau}}$ and the norm $|\dot{\gamma}_c(\tau)|$. For more details, see [28, sec. 10.4.2].

In formulæ, the monotonicity relationship between Ricci flow and optimal transportation, can be stated like this. Let ϵ , ϵ_1 , and ϵ_2 be real numbers such that $\frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon}} = \frac{1-\theta}{\sqrt{\epsilon_1}} + \frac{\theta}{\sqrt{\epsilon_2}}$, for $0 < \theta < 1$. Let us impose three measurable functions:

$$\zeta_{\mu_1}[\mathbb{R}] = \epsilon_1^{-\frac{n}{2}} \exp \left\{ -\frac{c\sqrt{\epsilon_1}}{-2(\theta-1)} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon}} + \frac{\theta}{\sqrt{\epsilon_2}} \right) \right\} \mathbb{B}(\sqrt{\epsilon_1}, x), \quad (14)$$

$$\zeta_{\mu_2}[\mathbb{R}] = \epsilon_2^{-\frac{n}{2}} \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2\sqrt{\epsilon_2}} \varphi_{\text{dis}}((x, 2\epsilon_1), (y, \epsilon_2)) \right\}, \quad (15)$$

$$\xi_\mu[\mathbb{R}] = \epsilon^{-\frac{n}{2}} \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2\sqrt{\epsilon}} \varphi_{\text{dis}}((x, 0), (y, \epsilon)) \right\}. \quad (16)$$

where c is a positive constant, $\mathbb{B}(\sqrt{\epsilon_1}, x)$ a ball of radius $\rho = \sqrt{\epsilon_1}$, φ_{dis} a function concerning the distance in relation to (13), and $x \in \mathcal{M}$ is a point. It holds that $\varphi_{\text{dis}}((x, 0), (x, \epsilon_1)) \leq c\sqrt{\epsilon_1}$ and $\varphi_{\text{dis}}((x, \epsilon_1), (x, 2\epsilon_1)) \leq c\sqrt{\epsilon_1}$, for any $x \in \mathbb{B}(\sqrt{\epsilon_1}, x)$.

The optimality of the Ricci flow depends on this inequality,

$$\int_{\mathcal{M}} \xi_\mu d\text{vol}_g(\epsilon) \geq \left(\int_{\mathcal{M}} \zeta_{\mu_1} d\text{vol}_g(\epsilon_1) \right)^{1-\theta} \left(\int_{\mathcal{M}} \zeta_{\mu_2} d\text{vol}_g(\epsilon_2) \right)^\theta, \quad (17)$$

for any geodesic, or better, ℓ -geodesic, in accordance with Perelman’s intuition,

$$\gamma_c : [\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2] \rightarrow \mathcal{M}(\rightarrow \mathbb{R}).$$

2. Agile Memorandum on the Kähler–Ricci Flow

The *Kähler–Ricci flow* is but a Ricci flow on a Kähler manifold [23], the formalism of which is

$$\phi_{\text{KR}}^{\text{unn}} = \frac{\partial g_{\mu\bar{\nu}}}{\partial t} = -R_{\mu\bar{\nu}}, \quad (18a)$$

$$\phi_{\text{KR}}^{\text{nor}} = \frac{\partial g_{\mu\bar{\nu}}}{\partial t} = -R_{\mu\bar{\nu}} + g_{\mu\bar{\nu}}. \quad (18b)$$

The metric

$$g_{\mu\bar{\nu}} \stackrel{\text{viz}}{=} g_{\mu\bar{\nu}}(t), \quad t \geq 0, \quad (19)$$

illustrates a solution to ϕ_{KR} in (18) under a 1-parameter family of biholomorphisms.

Let us remember that a Kähler manifold is a complex structure, and yet it can be determined as a Riemannian manifold of a special type. More carefully, a Kähler structure on a Riemannian manifold is a *symplectic manifold* $(\mathcal{M}, \omega_s) = (\mathbb{R}^{2n}, \omega_s)$ endowed with an integrable almost complex $\mathcal{J}_{\mathbb{C}|}$ -structure compatible with a symplectic form ω_s , i.e. a non-degenerate closed real-valued differential 2-form, the metric of which is Kählerian. From a Riemannian viewpoint, $\mathcal{J}_{\mathbb{C}|}$ is on a real manifold \mathcal{M} of dimension $2n$.

The symbol $\mathcal{J}_{\mathbb{C}|}$ denotes an *almost complex structure*,

$$x \mapsto \mathcal{J}_{\mathbb{C}|}: \mathcal{T}_x \mathcal{M} \xrightarrow{\text{linear map}} \mathcal{T}_x \mathcal{M}, \quad \mathcal{J}_{\mathbb{C}|}^2 = -\text{id}_{\mathcal{T}_x \mathcal{M}}, \quad (20)$$

$$\mathcal{J}_{\mathbb{C}|}: \mathring{\mathcal{T}} \mathcal{M} \xrightarrow{\text{linear map}} \mathring{\mathcal{T}} \mathcal{M}, \quad \mathcal{J}_{\mathbb{C}|}^2 = -\text{id}_{\mathring{\mathcal{T}} \mathcal{M}}, \quad (21)$$

coinciding with a smooth field of complex structures on the tangent spaces (20), or even with an automorphism on the tangent bundle (21).

2.1. Kähler–Ricci Flow as a Parabolic Complex Monge–Ampère Formula

Let $\mathfrak{v}_t \stackrel{\text{viz}}{=} \mathfrak{v}(t)$ be a \mathbb{R} -function on \mathcal{M} , so that

$$g_{\mu\bar{\nu}}(t) = g_{\mu\bar{\nu}}^0 + (\partial_\mu \bar{\partial}_\nu)_t \log \det(g_{\xi\bar{\varrho}}^0) + \partial_\mu \bar{\partial}_\nu \mathfrak{v}(t), \quad (22)$$

and then

$$R_{\mu\bar{\nu}} = -\frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^\mu \partial \bar{z}^\nu} \log \det(g_{\xi\bar{\varrho}}) = \overline{R_{\nu\bar{\mu}}}, \quad (23)$$

one gets

$$R_{\mu\bar{\nu}}(t) - R_{\mu\bar{\nu}}(0) = -\partial_\mu \bar{\partial}_\nu \log \frac{\det \left(g_{\xi\bar{\varrho}}^0 + (\partial_\xi \bar{\partial}_\varrho)_t \log \det(g_{\zeta\bar{\tau}}^0) + \partial_\xi \bar{\partial}_\varrho \mathfrak{v}(t) \right)}{\det \left(g_{\xi\bar{\varrho}}^0 \right)}. \quad (24)$$

It follows that

$$\partial_\mu \bar{\partial}_\nu \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathfrak{v} \right) = -R_{\mu\bar{\nu}} - \partial_\mu \bar{\partial}_\nu \log \det(g_{\xi\bar{\varrho}}^0) = \partial_\mu \bar{\partial}_\nu \log \frac{\det \left(g_{\xi\bar{\varrho}}^0 + (\partial_\xi \bar{\partial}_\varrho)_t \log \det(g_{\zeta\bar{\tau}}^0) + \partial_\xi \bar{\partial}_\varrho \mathfrak{v}(t) \right)}{\det \left(g_{\xi\bar{\varrho}}^0 \right)}. \quad (25)$$

The Kähler–Ricci flow (18) can be rewritten as a *parabolic complex Monge–Ampère formula* [27] [1]:

$$\frac{\partial \mathfrak{v}}{\partial t} = \log \frac{\det \left(g_{\xi\bar{\varrho}}^0 + (\partial_\xi \bar{\partial}_\varrho)_t \log \det(g_{\zeta\bar{\tau}}^0) + \partial_\xi \bar{\partial}_\varrho \mathfrak{v}(t) \right)}{\det \left(g_{\xi\bar{\varrho}}^0 \right)} + \mathfrak{v}_1(t), \quad (26)$$

for a constant value \mathfrak{v}_1 .

2.2. Kähler–Christoffel symbols

The Kähler–Christoffel symbols have this formal appearance:

$$\Gamma_{\mu\nu}^\xi = \frac{1}{2} g^{\xi\bar{\varrho}} \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial z^\mu} g_{\nu\bar{\varrho}} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z^\nu} g_{\mu\bar{\varrho}} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{z}^\varrho} g_{\mu\nu} \right\} = g^{\xi\bar{\varrho}} \frac{\partial}{\partial z^\mu} g_{\nu\bar{\varrho}}, \quad (27a)$$

$$\Gamma_{\mu\bar{\nu}}^\xi = \frac{1}{2} g^{\xi\bar{\varrho}} \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial z^\mu} g_{\bar{\nu}\bar{\varrho}} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{z}^\nu} g_{\mu\bar{\varrho}} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{z}^\varrho} g_{\mu\bar{\nu}} \right\} = 0, \quad (27b)$$

$$\Gamma_{\mu\nu}^\xi = \Gamma_{\nu\mu}^\xi. \quad (27c)$$

2.3. Geometric Curvature Evolution (in the Form of a Theorem)

Theorem 2.1. *A curvature that undergoes the action of the The Kähler–Ricci flow takes this expression:*

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \Delta_t \right) R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\theta}} &= -\frac{\partial^2 g_{\mu\bar{\nu}}}{\partial z^\xi \partial \bar{z}^\theta} + g^{\nu\bar{\nu}} \left(\frac{\partial g_{\mu\bar{\nu}}}{\partial z^\xi} \cdot \frac{\partial g_{\nu\bar{\nu}}}{\partial \bar{z}^\theta} \right) \\ &= R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\theta}} R_{\nu\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\theta}} - R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\theta}} R_{\nu\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\theta}} + R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\tau\bar{\nu}} R_{\nu\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\theta}} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} (-R_{\mu\bar{\nu}} R_{\nu\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\theta}}) - \frac{1}{2} R_{\nu\bar{\nu}} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\theta}} - \frac{1}{2} R_{\xi\bar{\xi}} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\nu\bar{\theta}} - \frac{1}{2} R_{\nu\bar{\nu}} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\theta}}. \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

Proof. By putting $\frac{\partial}{\partial t} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\theta}} = -\frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^\xi \partial \bar{z}^\theta} (\frac{\partial}{\partial t} g_{\mu\bar{\nu}}) = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^\xi \partial \bar{z}^\theta} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}} = \nabla_\xi \nabla_{\bar{\theta}} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}} - R_{\mu\bar{\nu}} R_{\xi\bar{\theta}\zeta\bar{\nu}}$, and thanks to the second Bianchi identity (38), we obtain two equational groups. The first one is

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_\xi \nabla_{\bar{\theta}} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}} &= \nabla_\xi \nabla_{\bar{\theta}} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\zeta\bar{\nu}} = \nabla_\xi \nabla_{\bar{\theta}} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\zeta\bar{\theta}} = \nabla_\xi \nabla_{\bar{\theta}} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\theta}} - R_{\xi\bar{\zeta}\mu\bar{\tau}} R_{\tau\bar{\nu}\zeta\bar{\theta}} + R_{\xi\bar{\zeta}\tau\bar{\nu}} R_{\mu\bar{\tau}\zeta\bar{\theta}} \\ &\quad - R_{\xi\bar{\zeta}\zeta\bar{\tau}} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\tau\bar{\theta}} + R_{\xi\bar{\zeta}\tau\bar{\theta}} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\zeta\bar{\tau}}; \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

the second group is

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{\bar{\zeta}} \nabla_{\zeta} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\theta}} &= \nabla_{\bar{\zeta}} \nabla_{\zeta} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\theta}} + R_{\xi\bar{\zeta}\mu\bar{\tau}} R_{\tau\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\theta}} - R_{\xi\bar{\zeta}\tau\bar{\nu}} R_{\mu\bar{\tau}\xi\bar{\theta}} + R_{\xi\bar{\zeta}\xi\bar{\tau}} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\tau\bar{\theta}} - R_{\xi\bar{\zeta}\tau\bar{\theta}} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\tau}} \\ &= \nabla_{\bar{\zeta}} \nabla_{\zeta} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\theta}} + R_{\mu\bar{\tau}} R_{\tau\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\theta}} - R_{\tau\bar{\nu}} R_{\mu\bar{\tau}\xi\bar{\theta}} + R_{\xi\bar{\tau}} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\tau\bar{\theta}} - R_{\tau\bar{\theta}} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\tau}}. \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

Let us combine (29) and (30):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\theta}} &= \nabla_{\bar{\zeta}} \nabla_{\zeta} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\theta}} - R_{\xi\bar{\zeta}\mu\bar{\tau}} R_{\tau\bar{\nu}\zeta\bar{\theta}} + R_{\xi\bar{\zeta}\tau\bar{\nu}} R_{\mu\bar{\tau}\zeta\bar{\theta}} - R_{\xi\bar{\tau}} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\tau\bar{\theta}} + R_{\xi\bar{\zeta}\tau\bar{\theta}} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\zeta\bar{\tau}} - R_{\mu\bar{\zeta}} R_{\xi\bar{\theta}\zeta\bar{\nu}} \\ &= \Delta R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\theta}} - R_{\xi\bar{\zeta}\mu\bar{\tau}} R_{\tau\bar{\nu}\zeta\bar{\theta}} + R_{\xi\bar{\zeta}\tau\bar{\nu}} R_{\mu\bar{\tau}\zeta\bar{\theta}} + R_{\xi\bar{\zeta}\tau\bar{\theta}} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\zeta\bar{\tau}} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} (-R_{\mu\bar{\tau}} R_{\tau\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\theta}}) - \frac{1}{2} R_{\tau\bar{\nu}} R_{\mu\bar{\tau}\xi\bar{\theta}} - \frac{1}{2} R_{\xi\bar{\tau}} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\tau\bar{\theta}} - \frac{1}{2} R_{\tau\bar{\theta}} R_{\mu\bar{\nu}\xi\bar{\tau}}, \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

as required. \square

Appendix

1. Einstein–Hilbert Action, or the Bare Gravitational Action

The Einstein–Hilbert action [20] [21] corresponds to

$$\mathcal{S}_{\text{EH}} = -\frac{c^4}{16\pi G_{\text{N}}} \int R_{\text{s}} \sqrt{-g} d^4 x = -\frac{1}{2\chi} \int_{\Omega \subset \mathbb{M}^4} R_{\text{s}} \sqrt{-g} d^4 x, \quad (32)$$

whilst the variation of \mathcal{S}_{EH} could be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \mathcal{S}_{\text{EH}} &= -\frac{1}{2\chi} \int_{\Omega \subset \mathbb{M}^4} \delta (R_{\text{s}} \sqrt{-g}) d^4 x = -\frac{1}{2\chi} \int_{\Omega \subset \mathbb{M}^4} \delta (g^{\mu\nu} R_{\mu\nu} \sqrt{-g}) d^4 x \\ &= -\frac{1}{2\chi} \int_{\Omega \subset \mathbb{M}^4} (R_{\mu\nu} \sqrt{-g} \delta g^{\mu\nu} + g^{\mu\nu} R_{\mu\nu} \delta \sqrt{-g} + g^{\mu\nu} \delta R_{\mu\nu} \sqrt{-g}) d^4 x \\ &= -\frac{1}{2\chi} \int_{\Omega \subset \mathbb{M}^4} \sqrt{-g} \left\{ \left(R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} R_{\text{s}} \right) \delta g^{\mu\nu} + g^{\mu\nu} \delta R_{\mu\nu} \right\} d^4 x \\ &= -\frac{1}{2\chi} \int_{\Omega \subset \mathbb{M}^4} \sqrt{-g} (G_{\mu\nu} \delta g^{\mu\nu} \delta R_{\mu\nu}) d^4 x. \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

The Eq. (32) is the action from which it is possible to reconstruct the Einstein field Eq. (34).

2. The Einstein Field Equations

The Einstein field equations [11, pp. 844-845] [12, § 4] are:

$$G_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R_s = \kappa T_{\mu\nu} \quad (34a)$$

$$= R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R_s = \frac{8\pi G_N}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}, \quad (34b)$$

$$= R_{\mu\nu} = \kappa \left(T_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}T \right), \quad (34c)$$

$$= -\frac{\partial}{\partial x_\xi} \left\{ \begin{matrix} \mu\nu \\ \xi \end{matrix} \right\} + \left\{ \begin{matrix} \mu\xi \\ \varrho \end{matrix} \right\} \left\{ \begin{matrix} \nu\varrho \\ \xi \end{matrix} \right\} + \frac{\partial^2 \log \sqrt{-g}}{\partial x_\mu \partial x_\nu} - \left\{ \begin{matrix} \mu\nu \\ \xi \end{matrix} \right\} \frac{\partial \log \sqrt{-g}}{\partial x_\xi}, \quad (34d)$$

where

- $G_{[\mu\nu]} = R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R_s$, $G_{[\mu\nu]} = G_{\mu\nu=\nu\mu}$ is the Einstein tensor,
- $R_{\mu\nu}$ is the Ricci curvature tensor (Margo 1.1),
- $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor,
- R_s is the scalar curvature, or Ricci scalar (4),
- $\kappa = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}$ is the Einstein (gravitational) constant [10], that is the strength of coupling between matter (physical dimension) and geometric space,
- $T_{\mu\nu}$ is the energy-momentum tensor, i.e. a quantity for the density of matter, which represents the presence of a *disturbance* in space-time,

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{-g}} \frac{\delta \left[\sqrt{-g} \mathcal{L} = \left(\sqrt{-g} \left(\frac{1}{2} g^{\mu\nu} \partial_{\mu F} \partial_{\nu F} - U \right) \right) \right]}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}}, \quad (35)$$

setting

$$\mathcal{L} \stackrel{\text{viz}}{=} \mathcal{L}_m = \frac{1}{2} \partial_{\mu F} \partial^{\mu} F - U(F), \quad \partial^{\mu} F = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial (\partial_{\mu} F)}, \quad (36)$$

designating the Lagrangian density of the matter-energy, with a scalar field F and a potential $U(F)$,

- G_N is the Newtonian constant of gravitation,
- $\left\{ \begin{matrix} \mu\nu \\ \xi \end{matrix} \right\}$ etc. are the Christoffel symbols of the second kind:^a

$$\left\{ \begin{matrix} \xi \\ \mu\nu \end{matrix} \right\} \stackrel{\text{viz}}{=} \Gamma^{\xi}_{\mu\nu} = g^{\xi\varrho} \Gamma^{\varsigma}_{\mu\nu} \left\langle \frac{\partial}{\partial x^{\varsigma}}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x^{\varrho}} \right\rangle = g^{\xi\varrho} \left\langle \nabla_{\frac{\partial}{\partial x^{\mu}}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^{\nu}}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x^{\varrho}} \right\rangle \quad (37a)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} g^{\xi\varrho} \left\{ \frac{\partial g_{\nu\varrho}}{\partial x^{\mu}} + \frac{\partial g_{\mu\varrho}}{\partial x^{\nu}} - \frac{\partial g_{\mu\nu}}{\partial x^{\varrho}} \right\} \quad (37b)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} g^{\xi\varrho} (g_{\nu\varrho,\mu} + g_{\mu\varrho,\nu} - g_{\mu\nu,\varrho}). \quad (37c)$$

3. The Second Bianchi Identity, aka Differential Identity

The second Bianchi identity presents this series of formulæ:

$$\left\{ \begin{matrix} \nabla_{\kappa} R_{\mu\nu\xi}^{\varrho} + \nabla_{\mu} R_{\nu\kappa\xi}^{\varrho} + \nabla_{\nu} R_{\kappa\mu\xi}^{\varrho} = 0, \end{matrix} \right. \quad (38a)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{matrix} \nabla_{[\kappa} R_{\mu\nu]} \xi^{\varrho} = 0, \end{matrix} \right. \quad (38b)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{matrix} \nabla_{\varsigma} R_{\mu\nu\xi\varrho} + \nabla_{\xi} R_{\mu\nu\varrho\varsigma} + \nabla_{\varrho} R_{\mu\nu\varsigma\xi} = 0, \end{matrix} \right. \quad (38c)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{matrix} \nabla_{[\varsigma]} R_{\mu\nu[\xi\varrho]} = 0, \end{matrix} \right. \quad (38d)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{matrix} R_{\mu\nu\xi\varrho;\varsigma} + R_{\mu\nu\varrho\varsigma;\xi} + R_{\mu\nu\varsigma\xi;\varrho} = 0, \end{matrix} \right. \quad (38e)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{matrix} R_{\mu\nu[\xi\varrho;\varsigma]} = 0. \end{matrix} \right. \quad (38f)$$

In (38e) (38f) the semi-colon is for a covariant derivative.

^a The Christoffel symbols are named after Elwin B. Christoffel; but their concomitant exposition is also available in R. Lipschitz [24].

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